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Email ID : rajwademandaldhule1@gmail.com

rajwademandaldhule2@gmail.com

कार्यालयीन वेळ

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A Study of Utilisation of Renewable Energy Sources- Roadmap Towards Sustainable Development in India

Dr. Jayasree Nambiar

Astt. Professor,

Balaji College of Arts, Commerce and Science, Pune

E-mail: jayapradeepnambiar@gmail.com

Abstract:

Indian economy was committed to attain sustainable economic development by way of developing renewable energy sources and reduce the emission intensities 45% by 2023. Expansion of renewable energy enables to address the energy concerns of the economy in the future and committed sustainable and equitable development process. Renewable energy sources like solar, thermal, ocean, biomass can meet the huge energy requirements of the highly populated economy. Out of total energy consumption, 42% is contributed by renewable sources. India is one of the countries in the world conducted various research to utilise the abundant quantities of the renewable energy sources to attain sustainable economic development. In this paper the researcher has tried to understand and analyse the renewable energy potential of the economy and the action plan needed to utilise it in full quantity.

Keywords: Renewable, Potentials, Solar, Biomass, abundant

Introduction:

Sustainable development necessitates the utilisation of renewable energy sources. India is having abundant source of solar, wind and hydro energy resources. Its availability automatically creates a favourable environment for implementation of renewable energy projects. As per statistics, India has an installed energy capacity of 176.5 GW and stands fourth largest among the world economies. The target of

achieving total 450 GW also set by the government by attracting competitive investment in water, solar and wind energy potentials.

National Solar mission introduced in 2010 has helped to scale up the solar energy generation in India. The other initiatives are 100% FDI under automatic route, ultra mega energy parks, standard bidding guidelines for competitive bidding based on tariff for grid connected projects. The philosophy of Atmanirbhar Bharat also intended to promote competitive investments in energy sector related research and innovation.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the role of renewable energy sources in sustainable development.
2. To analyse the status of India in developing renewable energy.
3. To understand the challenges in the implementation of renewable energy plants.

Review of literature:

One of the obstacles to the spread of renewable energy technologies is problem in the connectivity to the grid. So, the investors are showing lack of confidence in investing this area. This is the area India need to focus to attain sustainable development.(6)

The role of renewable energy in protection of environment needs to be studied and practiced by the world economies. It is not only supporting energy generation but also helps the economy to generate employability by developing business

opportunities to individuals. It also provides various health benefits to humanity along with sustainable economic benefits. (18)

Out of the various renewable energy sources such as wind and hydro power sources, solar is the least expensive source and can easily be installed. Coal based thermal power plants are expensive. In the case of wind and solar power plants, the construction time required is very less so the energy can be easily generated. The gift of nature can be utilised and benefitted to the growing population. (19)

Data Analysis:

1. Role of Renewable energy in sustainable development:

The renewable energy sources are the important parameters of Indian economic development. The world is witnessing a total change during the transformation towards sustainable circular economy. The use of renewable energy can reduce the negative impacts of change in climate and over dependence of fossil fuels. Exploring the treasure of renewable energy sources is the requirement of the day to meet the needs of present generation without disturbing the needs of future generation. The concept of sustainable development introduced in 1980s to ensure the access to resources to all without creating any harmful impact to the planet. The aim is to have a better and balanced socio-economic life and clean environment to all.

In India the huge demand for energy during the process of growth is partially satisfied by the availability of renewable energy resources. Ministry of power had initiated the National Electricity Plan [NEP] with a 10-year action plan. This was a part of strategy to ensure complete electrification even in remote villages with affordable price. Use of renewable energy helps to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions and improve energy security of the country for long

run. The coal powered plant emits 90% less greenhouse gases and pollutants compared to others. Renewable energy initiatives also increase employability. The following are the various ways these initiatives can contribute towards sustainable development.

Reducing Greenhouse Gas Emissions: Generation and use of renewable energy sources renewable energy can reduce the greenhouse gas emissions. It can reduce the climatic changes due to greenhouse gas emission. The excess dependence on fossil fuels leading to the release of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere.

Energy Security: increase in the capacity of renewable energy can reduce the dependence on fossil fuels and attain energy security too. The country is 2nd highest importer. The demand for energy increasing day by day. Exploiting the huge potential of renewable energy resources available in India can reduce the dependence on imported fuels and attain self-sufficiency in oil production.

Wide extend of Energy Access: renewable energy is produced from the natural resources; these are accessible to all. With simple technology anyone can produce energy for their day today activities. In the case of developing nations due to energy shortage people are deprived of better-quality life. Generation of renewable energy can improve the standard of living and reduce poverty.

Employability: The potential to generate employment opportunities are huge in renewable energy industry. The manufacturing and installation of renewable energy plants require skilled labour. Solar plant installation is very popular in rural areas also. It has created lot of opportunities so far.

Promoting Rural Development: It can support rural population by providing continuous energy supply, use of modern amenities of life and medical facilities. This will improve the quality of life of the population and help to increase agricultural productivity.

Ensuring a Sustainable Future: The country can ensure a clean energy source and attain a better future life for the future generation. The collaborative efforts of industry, government and foreign sectors can bring a pollution free life to the present generation through exploring maximum renewable energy sources. This will reduce the climatic imbalance affecting agricultural production and severe health issues faced by the mankind.

2. India's energy consumption and Government initiatives in investments in renewable energy:

India is the 3rd largest energy consuming country; 4th place in renewable installed country and 4th in solar and wind power capacity. Year on year growth in renewable energy marked 9.83% in 2022. Installed capacity of non-fossil category has increased 396% in the last 8.5 years (179.57 GW). The

installed solar energy capacity increased by 30 times in the last 9 years (72.31 GW). The installed hydro energy capacity has increased by 128% as on November 2023 data. Further to promote investment in renewable energy, up to 100% FDI is allowed under automatic route based on The Electricity Act 2003. Green energy corridor scheme for energy requirements of small industries and customers, an allotment of \$ 3.2Bn for solar PV manufacturing are other initiatives. Several other measures include Green Term Ahead Market (G-TAM) to facilitate sale of renewable energy, PM KUSUM scheme, Solar rooftop schemes and incentives to bio energy and small hydro power enablers. Green hydrogen mission is another initiative to produce 5 MMT by 2030. To achieve that an incentive worth \$ 2.12 Bn has been offered to maximise energy production to cope up with the expected energy consumption.

The following is the installed capacity for Renewables as of Nov 2023:

Wind power	44.5 GW	
Solar Power	72.3 GW	
Biomass/Co-generation	10.2 GW	
Small Hydro Power	4.98 GW	
Waste To Energy	0.57 GW	
Large Hydro	46.88 GW	
Installed generation capacity (sector wise) as on 31.05.2023		
Sector	MW	% of Total
Central Sector	1,00,055	24.0%
State Sector	1,05,726	25.3%
Private Sector	2,11,887	50.7%
Total	4,17,668	

Source: www.investindia.gov.in

Installed generation capacity (fuel wise) as on 31.05.2023		
Category	Installed generation capacity(mw)	% of share in Total
Wind, Solar & Other RE	125,692	30.2 %
Wind	42,868	10.3 %
Solar	67,078	16.1 %
BM Power/Cogen	10,248	2.5 %
Waste to Energy	554	0.1 %
Small Hydro Power	4,944	1.2 %

Source: Central Electricity Authority (CEA) powermin.gov.in

Union Budget 2023 Highlights :

Union budget 2023 proposed to implement many green initiatives, mentioned as SAPTARISHI (7 priorities). It includes \$2.4 Bn for national hydrogen mission, \$ 36 Mn additional allotment and 4 GWh battery energy storage system. \$1.02/2.5 Bn Central Sector Support for ISTS Infrastructure for 13 GW Renewable Energy from Ladakh. Other initiatives are favourable incentives, affordable financing options, solar parks, and dedicated investor facilitation channels. The objective is to make India as one of the most attractive destinations for setting up renewable energy plants. India is actively forecasting and scheduling renewable power, promoting reliable storage solutions, and banking facilities to ensure adequate grid connectivity and round the clock power supply.

Production Linked Incentive (PLI) Scheme :

The Union Cabinet has given its approval to introduce the Production-Linked Incentive (PLI) Scheme in High Efficiency Solar PV Modules for Enhancing India's Manufacturing Capabilities and Enhancing Exports under Aatmanirbhar Bharat. The national programme on high-efficiency solar PV modules includes Tranche 1: INR 4500 cr (US\$ 550 Mn), Tranche 2: INR 19,500 cr (US\$ 2.37 Bn). The second phase, launched on 21st September 2022, is expected to build 65 GW of annual manufacturing capacity. The National Green Hydrogen Mission with an outlay of INR 19,744 Cr (US\$ 2.4 Bn) targets 5 MMT annual green hydrogen/ ammonia production by 2030. The scheme focuses on Direct employment of about 30,000 and Indirect employment of about 1,20,000 persons; Import substitution of around INR 17,500 Cr every year, and impetus to Research & Development to achieve higher efficiency in solar PV modules. Today, India offers one of the lowest tariffs worldwide,

ranging \$ 0.031-0.037/kWh. Public Private partnership is ensured to accomplish the task with minimum challenges.

Investment in Indian Renewables - Avenues for foreign companies :

There are various avenues available for foreign investors in renewable energy sector in India. They can invest in direct project development allowing them to have more controls and expected revenue. Through direct bidding for government tenders the foreign investors can easily avail benefits of government policies such as incentives, tax concessions and future purchase agreements. Technology transfer and skill development are some other advantages to India as a host country. India is promoting joint ventures and partnerships with foreign companies in renewable energy projects. The foreign investors can avail financing options in collaboration with Indian companies and be a part of renewable energy initiatives.

Growth outlook of renewable energy - Proposal for future :

1. Investment: ¹ 74,000 crores of investment are sanctioned to install 13.5 GW renewable energy capacity.

2. National Green Hydrogen Mission: Government approved this mission worth ¹ 19,744 crores of expenditure on 4th January 2023. The objective is to increase production and export of Green Hydrogen and its derivatives.

3. Green Energy Corridor: This consists of Inter-State Transmission System for 13 GW RE Projects in Ladakh. The MNRE plans to set up 13,000 MW RE along with 12000 MWh Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) and despatch power to other states.

4. PLI Scheme for High Efficiency: The aim is to achieve the manufacturing capacity of Giga Watt (GW) scale in the High Efficiency Solar PV Modules. Under this government plans to set

up 39,600 MW of fully / partially integrated solar PV module manufacturing units.

5. Wind Energy: India is surrounded by water on three sides and has good potential for offshore wind energy generation. The 7600 km coastline enables to produce wind energy and India plans to generate 37 GW capacity of Offshore Wind Energy in 2023-24.

6. Solar Parks: The Scheme for "Development of Solar Parks and Ultra Mega Solar Power Projects" was rolled out in December 2014, with aggregate capacity 20,000 MW. As on 30-11-2023, Ministry has approved 50 solar parks with an aggregate capacity of around 37,490 MW in 12 States across the country.

7. PM KUSUM: Expansion of PM Kusum without state control with a target of 49 lakhs pump to be installed or solarised capacity.

8. Rooftop Solar: Under this program, 741 MW capacity has been installed and operational and an additional 2.77 GW capacity installed with government and private participation.

9. Bioenergy Initiative: Bio energy projects with 105 MW energy capacity has been installed in northern states of India in 2023. This initiative is intended to spread the message of waste to energy project. Government proposed to install 46000 number of biogas plants during 2023-24.

10. Renewable Energy Implementation Agencies (REIAs) are allowed an annual bidding trajectory for RE power bids as prescribed by Ministry of new and renewable energy.

11. Renewable Purchase Obligation (RPO): Under energy conservation act 2001, Government of India allowed renewable purchase obligation (RPO) targets for some identified customers.

12. IREDA: RBI has granted an 'Infrastructure Finance Company (IFC)' status to Indian Renewable Energy Development Agency. The shares of the company listed

on NSE and BSE. The IPO marked with good response from investors.

Source: pib.gov.in

Renewable Energy in India :

India, with a population of 1.3 billion attained self-sufficiency in energy production. 42 % of the demand for energy from the growing population is met by the renewable energy sources. It ranks 3rd largest energy producer in the world with sustainable development process. Sustainable energy concept in India started with hydroelectric projects. Now India is the fifth nation globally in potential hydroelectricity generating capacity. Started with Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC) India has domestically developed nuclear reactors and secured 4th place in wind power generating capacity in the world. Solar energy solutions introduced in India are based on environmental sustainability. There is a platform established known as International Solar Alliance (ISA) to boost the solar energy production. Being a developing country, biomass is another option to renewable carbon neutral energy source and also supports rural employability. Renewable energy is the requirement of the day as the world is facing inflation due to increase in coal prices globally and Russia-Ukraine conflict. In the domain of decentralized renewable energy, various sectors show promise for substantial expansion, propelled by policy reforms addressing current challenges and enticing incentives on the demand side.

Public sector undertakings (PSUs): Government of India's initiatives to install renewable energy plants are taken care by the public sector undertakings. These organisations aim to decarbonize their production process and contribute to sustainable development. Non-power sector PSUs, including Oil and Natural Gas Corporation (ONGC), Indian Oil Corporation (IOC), Bharat Petroleum

Corporation Limited (BPCL), and GAIL, have set a combined target for renewable capacity additions of 16.5GW by 2030. On the demand side, green hydrogen emerges as a significant force poised to drive India's clean energy ambitions. Corporations like the Adani Group and Reliance Industries have strongly supported the country's green hydrogen policy, announced in June 2022, and its 5 MTPA target, with several significant commitments. In India with a coastline stretching approximately 7,600 km, offering the potential to install around 195 GW of offshore wind capacity, this segment could contribute significantly to India's clean energy objectives. Lastly, the uptake of electric vehicles, projected to be a multi-billion-dollar opportunity in the country, will serve as a major demand-side driver for clean electricity generation assets.

The transformation to renewable energy in India is fast implementing over the last 10 years. The fast-growing economy could uplift the living standards of millions of its population from poverty. The growing population necessitates more development and infrastructure. Coal and oil have so far served as bedrocks of India's industrial growth and modernisation, giving a rising number of Indian people access to modern energy services. This includes adding new electricity connections for 50 million citizens each year over the past decade. Annual emission of CO₂ in India increased due to the high dependence on fossil fuel. India is third highest energy consuming country in the world. The individual CO₂ emission is less compared to that of emitters from world's developed countries. But the average energy consumption per person in India is less compared to that of United states. There is an increase in the energy demands in India since the last 10 year and it is going to increase further in the coming decades.

The clean energy initiative of India is going to achieve more than the target decided to achieve in COP 21- Paris Summit. The renewable energy

generating sources contributes 42% of the power requirements in India leading to achieve the dream of clean energy. The share of solar and wind energy increased tremendously due to technological development. India is world's largest producers of bio energy and huge potential to increase the production. IEA's analysis shows that the country is going to achieve the first position in ethanol market after United states and Brazil.

Favourable factors:

Government of India introduced various policy measures so far. The full implementation of these policies can help in achieving sustainable development. The subsidies for electric vehicle introduced in 2019 is helpful to encourage people to reduce energy use. Energy efficiency programs successfully reducing energy use and followed emissions especially from major industries and transport. Government also supported many villagers by distributing fuel gas cooking gas. This initiative helped to reduce the use of traditional biomass and firewood.

To benefit to the people of India, the policies can be well defined and whereby the trade-off between affordability, security and sustainability can be reduced. The production of green hydrogen can play an important role to decarbonize industrial sector. India can become a global hub for production and export of green hydrogen. If the overhead expenses are met, India can produce and meet 5 million tonne green hydrogen demand thereby replacing grey hydrogen in the refineries and fertiliser sector. These 5 million tonnes will result in abatement of 28 million tonnes of CO₂.

As a large developing economy with over 1.3 billion people, India's climate adaptation and mitigation ambitions are not just transformational for India but for the entire planet. NITI Aayog and IEA are committed to work together to enable India to grow, industrialize and provide a better quality of life to its citizens.

Challenges :

India is facing many challenges to achieve its target in renewable energy production. The expenses are not affordable to the country due to increase in commodity prices. As a highly populated country, India is facing lack of energy security, forces her to import energy. India is the third largest energy importer in the world. The availability and use of traditional energy sources for cooking and other purposes affecting the quality of life of the people. This also leading to poor air quality.

Renewables need natural resources :

As the production of renewable energy increases, the stress on natural resources will increase. The study conducted by institute for energy economics and financial analysis, the land requirement for solar and wind infrastructure will be around 25000 square kilometres by 2050. This may increase the stress on land and lead to land conflicts. In 2020, after a case filed by the local community, Rajasthan High Court had to order a stay on the 1500 MW Fatehgarh Ultra Mega Solar Park in Jaisalmer district. The marginalised farmers claimed that these lands they have been using for their livelihood but the state government claims control over the land and categorises it as a waste land. If this type of conflicts arises, it will be difficult for the state government to implement solar plants. The common lands which people used for their livelihood may also reduce.

Another case is that of the great Indian bustard, a critically endangered bird species that was threatened due to renewable energy infrastructure coming up in its habitat. Residents and RE companies have been at loggerheads over the issue. A similar case took place in Maharashtra where the Mumbai High Court, in 2010, directed the state to prohibit new windmills inside the Koyna Wildlife Sanctuary where windmills had been established illegally,

in violation of the Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972, and the area where they were set up was falling within a reserve, making it in violation of the Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980 as well.

The requirement of water for maintaining solar panel is another concern. A joint study by The Energy Resource Institute (TERI) and Niti Aayog has estimated that India will need at least 0.35 BCM water to clean solar panels by 2025. India has achieved 64 GW of solar capacity. MNRE has realised that excess water usage for cleaning solar panels exists in several states of India and pushing for judicious use of the precious resource. The government must find a balance between promoting the sector and ensuring it is environment-friendly, human rights are protected, and it is sustainable.

Suggestions:

As the share of renewable energy capacity integrated into the grid increases, understanding these dynamics becomes increasingly vital. This explanation delves into how renewables interface with the grid, their impact on grid operations, and the implications of high renewables penetration for future grid management.

Utility-Scale Generation :

The centralised renewable energy plants can generate can generate hundreds of megawatts (MW) of power. This can be distributed to business and households through systematic distribution channels. But the renewable resources are non-dispatchable as they rely on variable resources like sunlight and wind, which fluctuate throughout the day. Nevertheless, when renewable energy sources are available, priority is given to dispatching them in the order of preference. Wind and solar energy, having zero fuel costs, are utilized first as they represent the most cost-effective energy sources at the time.

Distributed Generation:

On the opposite end of the spectrum, small-scale residential and commercial renewables typically range from 5 to 500 kilowatts (KW). Predominantly consisting of solar panels, these distributed resources are often installed on-site at homes or businesses. Unlike large centralized renewable plants connected via high-voltage transmission lines, distributed resources link to the grid through electrical lines on the lower voltage distribution network, the same lines delivering electricity to consumers. The renewable energy projects operate mainly for onsite consumption such as rooftop solar systems powering households and business, not for commercial purposes. These small projects need to be organized well to increase power supply instead of reducing electricity demand. Community-scale renewables, larger than rooftop projects but smaller than utility-scale facilities, also connect to the grid through distribution lines, constituting distributed generation. Unlike small rooftop renewables, community-scale projects operate "in front of the meter," feeding generated power into the distribution grid for use by nearby homes and businesses.

Several strategies enhance grid flexibility and bolster renewable resource integration:

Renewable energy production requires provision of energy storage to store the seasonal excess produce and connected through the distribution grid. Expanding transmission lines connecting areas rich in renewable resources with high electricity demand enhances renewable resource value and reduces generation uncertainties.

Another solution is to balance energy production is to construct the grid leveraging multiple renewables, including solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal.

Creating awareness among the customers regarding availability, renewable energy

generation and sustainability, reducing demand during peak hours with storage facilities can reduce demand spikes. Wholesale power markets valuing generator flexibility incentivize grid adaptability. For instance, California has developed flexible ramping products (FRP) rewarding generators for their ability to ramp power quickly.

The new focus may be on the Lithium reserves in J&K's Salal- Haimana area of Reasi District explored by the Geological Survey of India (GSI). Lithium inferred resources (G3) of 5.9 million tonnes found in the area. This is the rare earth material which is used in manufacturing of batteries widely used in electric vehicles, smartphones and other electronic equipment.

Conclusion:

A complete shift in business organisation is needed to attend sustainable development in India. The circular economy model can promise the opportunity to sustainability by way of renewable energy sources and maintaining clear environment. The Government recognized and announced the focus areas for renewable generation. This includes renewable energy component manufacturing viz, hydrogen electrolyzers, battery storage, solar modules which in turn increases employability. Green energy corridor, green hydrogen production, pumped storage hydro, rooftop solar power and utility-scale battery storage are some other examples. With the future prospects of 500 GW RE capacity installation by 2030 and Net-Zero emissions by 2070 India announced one of the most accelerated energy transition plans in the world. With a growing population and ambitious renewable energy goals, India presents abundant investment opportunities and avenues for expansion in the renewable energy sector.

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